

THE INVESTIGATION OF THE BEHAVAIOR OF
LAMINATES SUBJECT TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

Zheng Chuanchao Zhang Kaida
Department of Aircraft Engineering
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xian P.R.C. 710072

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated theoretically and experimentally the behavior of fibre reinforced plastic composite laminates subject to low velocity impact. A new model was proposed for the analysis of damages. It took into account not only the coupling between tension and shear but also coupling between tension and bending. A finite element programme was developed to predicte the maximum impact force during impacting and impact induced damages for a given impact energy. Experimentally, a drop weight apparatus was designed to carry out low velocity impact. The history of impact force and the displacement versus time were measured. Nondestructive testing was conducted on the laminates. It was found that the combination of holographic method and X-ray method could determine the existence of damages, locate them easily and show their shape and size accurately. Compressive tests showed that impact induced damages sharply reduce the compressive strengh of the laminates. The numerical results agreed well with the experimental data obtained in this investigation.

KEYWORDS: Laminate; Low Velocity Impact; Nondestructive Testing; Damages; Finite Element Simulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main problems arising from the application of composite materials to structures is its low resistance to impact loads. Under low velocity impact, there is no obvious change on the surface of laminates, but inside the laminates, debouding, matrix cracks and delaminations occur often. These damages may sharply reduce the compressive strengh of the laminates. Greszczuk ⁽¹⁾ made a comprehensive study on the damages in composite materials due to low velocity impact. His experiments showed that the impact induced damages are similar to the damages caused by the static indentation. References ^(2, 3) verified that simple bending thory and quasi static state assumption could be used to predict the critical impact energy inducing damage in the case of low velocity impact. Shivakumur, Elber and Illg ⁽⁴⁾ considered the quasi isotropic discal plate impacted at the center. Assuming that the deformation of the

plates was symmetric, they analysed the damage by finite element methods. Later on ⁽⁵⁾ they proposed an Energy-Balance model for the prediction of impact force and duration due to low velocity impact on circular composite laminates. Wu and Springer ^(6, 7) studied the delamination by three-dimension finite element method. Their numerical results revealed that delamination was mainly due to the interlaminar normal stresses.

Although a lot of work has been done, many problems of low velocity impact are still open to study, especially the simulation of low velocity impact and the determination of damages in laminates. In this paper, a new bending model was proposed for the analysis of damages in laminates. Experiments were conducted on the low velocity impact. Damages were detected using nondestructive holographic method and X-ray nondestructive method.

2. THEORY

2.1 Description of the Problem Figure 1 is a rectangular plate (length L , width W , thickness H) made of a continuous fibre reinforced organic matrix composite. The plate consists of n plies or laminae. The ply orientation is arbitrary, and 0° ply is always in consistent with X -coordinate. The positive ply orientation is counterclockwise from the X -coordinate when the plate is viewed from the above. Perfect bonding between each ply is assumed.

FIGURE 1. Model

2.2 Basic Assumptions a. The laminates are linear elastic and small deformation assumption is adopted. b. Low velocity impact problem is treated as a quasi static problem. c. The deformation of every laminae satisfies Reissner's linear assumption. d. The impactor is rigid. e. The Energy-Balance model ⁽⁵⁾ is employed in the simulation of low velocity impact. That is to say, the potential energy of the impactor is equated to the sum of energies due to shear, bending and membrane deformations. The energy losses due to material damping, surface friction and higher mode vibrations are neglected. The impact energy is defined as the multiplication of the weight of the impactor and the difference between impact height and rebounding height.

2.3 Stiffness Matrix The stiffness matrix is derived in two steps. In the first step, the principle of minimum total potential energy is used to formulate the stiffness matrix for each lamina. In order to include the coupling between tension and bending, the inplane deformation must be considered.

For inplane deformation, eight-node isoparameter elements are employed, the quasi three-dimension elements degenerated from the twenty-node block elements ⁽⁸⁾ are em-

ployed to derive the bending stiffness matrix, the coupling between tension and shear is considered. Figure 2 is the i th element in j th lamina, each node having five freedom. The stiffness matrix is 40×40 . Since the local coordinates x - y locate in the symmetric plane, the stiffness matrix for the inplane deformation and bending can be set up separately.

FIGURE 2. The i th element in j th ply

In the second step, equivalent transformation⁽⁹⁾ is performed on elements of each lamina to establish the stiffness matrix for the laminate. The equivalent transformation is based on the parallel-axis theory. It has two aims: (1) considering the coupling between tension and bending; (2) reducing the freedom of the model (see Figure 3)

FIGURE 3. Equivalent transformation

2.4 Impact Force and Failure Criteria The distribution of impact force is assumed to be in the form of $q_{x,y} = q_0 \sqrt{1 - (\frac{x}{a})^2 - (\frac{y}{b})^2}$ a, b are the minor and major axes of the elliptic contact area obtained from the experiments⁽¹⁾.

An element is failed if the stresses in the element satisfies the Tsai-Wu inequality. The mode of failure is determined by maximum stress criteria: $\sigma_1 / X_t \geq 1$ fibre fail;

$\sigma_2 / Y_t \geq 1$ transverse splitting; $\tau_{12} / S_{12} \geq 1$ shear splitting and for compressive stresses $\sigma_1 / X_c \geq 1$ fibre crushing; $\sigma_2 / Y_c \geq 1$ matrix crushing. Elements that failed by splitting are considered to have lost their transverse and shear modulus. Hence the reduced moduli ($E_2 = G_{12} = 0$) are used in the failed elements in subsequent steps of the analysis.

2.5 Numerical Procedure Numerical results in the present analysis are obtained using an incremental transverse deflection procedure (see Figure 4). Frontal wave method is adopted. The failure region is calculated on a ply-by-ply basis. After the appropriate elastic moduli in the failed region are reduced, the analysis is repeated for

the next increment of impact load ΔP . The step-by-step procedure is as shown in Figure 4

FIGURE 4. Flow diagram of the numerical procedure

2.6 Numerical Example For comparison with the experiments, Assume that $L = 180\text{mm}$, $W = 50\text{mm}$, $H = 2\text{mm}$, stack sequence: $[+45 / -45 / 0 / 90 / +45 / -45 / 0 / 90]$ s. The elastic properties of lamina and lamina strength are list in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1 ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF LAMINA

Materials	Modulus GPa					Poisson ratio ν
	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	G_{23}	G_{31}	
T300 / 648	136.5	9.45	5.40	5.40	5.40	0.32

TABLE 2 LAMINA STRENGTH MPa

Longitudinal		Transverse		Shear
X_t	X_c	Y_t	Y_c	S_{12}
1100.	-840.	32.	-130.	67.

Details of the finite element mesh is shown in Figure 5. There are altogether 465 elements, 1488 nodes.

FIGURE 5. Finite element mesh

FIGURE 6. Damage region of No. 2 specimen (Area: 7.5cm^2)

FIGURE 7. Maximum impact force versus impact energy

TABLE 3 DAMAGE AREA OF EACH LAMINA (cm^2)

Layer	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Damages	1.75	1.87	1.75	1.75	6.13	4.0	2.5	2.6	7.1	4.9	3.6	4.3	7.4	6.7	5.3	5.6

Figure 6 is the calculated damage region when the impact energy is 3.15J . The damage in each lamina is listed in Table 3. Figure 7 shows the relationship between maximum impact force and impact energy. The critical energy inducing failure is 0.93J .

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Materials and Apparatus

The composite laminates used are T300 / 648 quasi isotropic 16-ply laminates, stacked by $[+45 / -45 / 0 / 90 / +45 / -45 / 0 / 90]_s$. The cured plates are nominally 2mm thick. The elastic modulus of lamina and lamina strength are listed in Table 1 and Table 2. The size of the specimen is $200 \times 75\text{mm}^2$. After four edges clamped on the fixture (see Figure 8), the impact area becomes $180 \times 50\text{mm}^2$. A drop weight apparatus (see Figure 8) is designed to carry out the low velocity impact. The movable plate is set to separate the impactor and the specimen after rebounding of the impactor to avoid repeated impacting. The impactor is steel cylinder with a hemispherical head. The mass of it is 0.5225kg .

FIGURE 8. Schematical view of the apparatus

3.2 Experimental Procedure Lift the carriage on which the impactor hung to the desired height, then release the switch. The impactor falls vertically down and impacts the specimen. After the impactor rebounds up, the movable plate is controlled to separate the specimen and the impactor. Table 4 is two typical specimen.

TABLE 4 TWO TYPICAL SPECIMEN

No.	Impact height(m)	Rebounding height(m)	Impact energy(J)
1	1.0	0.60	2.10
2	1.10	0.50	3.15

The centre of the upper surface of the specimen is impacted. On the center of the lower surface, a ring displacement transducer is fixed. At the points of 50mm away from the impact point along the longitudinal symmetric line of the lower surface, a pair of strain gauges are stuck. During impacting, the outputs of the strain gauge and ring transducer are detected by K54 monitor and DSS6521 digital oscilloscope. The corresponding curves for No. 2 specimen are as follows.

FIGURE 9. The output of the strain on the laminate

FIGURE 10. The output of the strain on the ring
After impacting, the magnitude of the impact force can be determined based on statically scaled curve (see Figure 11)

FIGURE 11. Scaled curve

Assuming the strain output is proportional to the impact force during impacting, the maximum impact force is 2160N. From Figure 7, the maximum impact force corresponding to impact energy 3.15J is approximately 2370N. The numerical result agrees well with the experimental data. The jumps in Figure 10 and Figure 9 is supposed to correspond to the start of damages. Energy needed to cause damages is 0.80J.

3.3 Nondestructive Testing Holographic method and X-ray method are employed to detect the damage in the specimen before and after impacting. When the holographic method is used, the specimen is clamped on one end and heated by electric heat blower. Real time method and double exposure method are used to record the lateral deformation of the specimen. Uniform fringe in the Figure 12a shows that the No. 2 specimen before impact is free of damages. The distorted fringe in Figure 12b shows impact induced damages inside the No. 2 specimen. The location and size of damage region are determined by the distorted fringe. Comparing Figure 12a and Figure 12b, the damage region inside No. 2 specimen is about 7.0cm^2 , slightly lower than the calculated results in Figure 6. The discrepancy is due to the inappropriate assumption of neglecting the energy losses from frictions.

FIGURE 12. Hologram

When X-ray radiography is used, it is generally necessary to drill a small hole in the center of the damage region (judged from Figure 12b), then drop an X-ray opaque penetrant in the hole. Figure 13 is a penetrant enhanced radiography of the damaged laminate. Comparing with Figure 12, the shape and size of the damage region are more clear. The damage region is 6.9cm^2 .

FIGURE 13. X-ray radiography

3.4 Compressive Tests In order to study the influence of the damages on the compressive strength of the laminates, compressive tests are performed. The buckling failure during compression is prevented. The compressive strength reduction is shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5 REDUCTION OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

No.	Compressive strength reduction
1	55.6%
2	56.9%

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. A new computational model is proposed based on the Reinsler's bending theory. The model takes into account not only the anisotropy in each lamina, but also the coupling between tension and bending in the laminates. A programme is developed to analyse the damage inside the arbitrarily plied laminates under certain impact energy. The maximum force during impact and the critical energy causing damage can be

predicted.

2. A drop weight apparatus is designed to carry out low velocity impact. The history of impact force versus time and the displacement versus time are measured. The magnitude of impact force is scaled quasi statically.
3. Two nondestructive methods are employed to detect the damage inside the laminate. It is found that combination of holographic method and X-ray method can not only determine the existence of damage, locate it easily, but also show its size, shape accurately.
4. Impact induced damages will sharply reduce the compressive strength of the laminates.
5. Good agreement of numerical results with test data shows that the model developed in this paper is workable and valuable.

5. REFERENCES

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